

An advanced predictive battery control strategy for plus energy building flexibility: Simulation-based assessment and laboratory experimental setup

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ABSTRACT

Buildings account for 40% of energy use making them central to achieving climate neutrality goals. In this context, energy building flexibility emerges as a key enabler, particularly when combined with the Plus Energy Building (PEB) concept, where buildings generate more renewable energy than they consume annually to achieve climate-neutrality goals. As an energy system, the building can offer demand-side flexibility by responding to external penalty signals such as price, CO₂ emissions or grid congestion, thus enabling system operators to dynamically influence consumption patterns. In this work, we present a predictive advanced PV-battery management strategy in year-long simulations across different scenarios, obtained by combining a reference building archetype, various representative European geo-clusters, and electrical consumption resulting from tailored controls of the thermal assets. The heterogeneous results across geo-clusters underscore the influence of climate, culture, and system sizing on predictive control performance, with findings from the Mediterranean cluster (with expected best case flexibility improvement in the range of 14%). These outcomes motivate the implementation of a laboratory-scale setup to port the proposed control strategies to commercially available devices under real working conditions. We report observations of a year-long monitoring of such a laboratory setup, recording the ability to shift battery stored energy toward high-priced periods, with non-standard induced inverter operations observed 10% of the time, highlighting the system's responsiveness under real-world conditions.

1. Introduction

1.1. General context

In 2025, the EU reached about 400 GW of solar capacity with residential PV adding about 9 GW [1] (14% of new installations), while battery storage climbed to about 75 GWh (half in homes) supported by over 3 million residential units connected to European grids within three years [2]. By 2030, solar is projected to reach 700 GW and storage is expected to scale tenfold from current capacity toward ambitious targets that, in light of today's growth trajectory, face significant challenges. Within the EU, the building stock consumes 40% of all energy and contributes 36% of carbon emissions across various phases including development, occupancy, renovation, and disposal [3]. Therefore, advancing energy efficiency measures in the built environment serves as a fundamental strategy for realizing the 2050 climate neutrality targets. In electricity distribution grids, the increasing deployment of renewable generation and the widespread uptake of technologies such as electric

vehicles and heat pumps are pushing the system from a passive to an active role [4]. A similar transformation is required for buildings to play a role in the energy transition thus adapting to the surrounding changes and potentially gaining not only better energy exploitation but also energy system resiliency [5]. Referring to the classification methods outlined in [6], it becomes feasible to identify five strategies for demand-side management within buildings, each related to the capacity to diminish, offload, reposition, adjust, or produce distributed energy resources (DERs) on-site. While flexibility is gaining prominence, its interpretation differs depending on the application's context and the system's level [5]. Here, we restrict the context to focus on the building sector, aligned with existing literature [6]. The IEA EBC Annex 67 introduces the concept of 'Energy Flexible Building', defined as: "a building able to manage its demand and generation in accordance with local climate conditions, user needs and grid requirements and will thus allow for demand side management/load control and thereby demand response based on the requirements of the surrounding grids" [7].

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Nomenclature

List of Abbreviations

BEMS	Building energy management system
BESS	Battery energy storage system
CAPEX	Capital expenditure
COP	Coefficient of performance
DER	Distributed energy resources
DHW	Domestic hot water
DoD	Depth of discharge
DR	Demand response
EPBD	Energy performance of buildings directive
EV	Electric vehicle
FF	Flexibility factor
GA	Genetic algorithm
HP	Heat pump
HPT	High-priced time
KPI	Key performance indicator
LP	Linear programming
ML	Machine learning
NLP	Non linear programming
nZEB	Net zero energy building
OPEX	Operating expenditure
PAC	Predictive advanced control
PEB	Plus energy building

PSO	Particle swarm optimization
PV	Photovoltaic
QP	Quadratic programming
RBC	Rule-based control
RES	Renewable energy resources
SC	Self-consumption
SCPI	Standard commands for programmable instruments
SoC	State of charge
SP	Self-production

List of symbols

\hat{E}_k	Predicted energy imported from the grid at the k-iteration time
A, B	Exponential zone coefficients
C_k	Cost signal
E_0	Battery constant voltage
f	Cost function
F_{KPI}	Flexibility key performance indicator
H_c	Control horizon
H_p	Prediction horizon
K	Polarization constants
k	Iteration time
P_{load}	Power load
P_{PV}	PV production power
R_0	Internal resistance

Flexibility in buildings arises from the ability to control the operation of specific systems without compromising the quality of the services they provide, while maintaining user comfort within acceptable limits [5]. The first requisite to enable the exploitation of such potential is the effective presence of enabling technologies [8] which are organized next into four technical factors with a specific focus on the electrical domain. First of all, the presence of renewable energy sources, PV systems in primis [1]. Secondly, the possibility to couple this local generation with battery electrical storage systems (BESS). A third factor considers the presence of deferrable loads. While many appliances can be included in this category, a critical role has been taken in recent years by large loads such as EVs and HPs, which add to the wider and more established category of thermostatically controlled loads [6]. These are bridge technologies from the electrical to the thermal domain, effectively expanding storage practices also to the thermal energy [9]. A final key factor is presented by the building energy management system (BEMS) which is expected to be able to both interact with and manage the systems behind-the-meter as well as process external inputs (e.g., from the grid, the market, the aggregator). Energy consumption patterns have a close link with the performance of daily life practices related to living in the building [10]. On this stimulus, literature has explored the call to active participation and involvement of the consumers (often addressed as *prosumers* [5]) in flexibility practices [11,12]. Nonetheless, it remains valuable but a complex and multi-domain problem which is not further considered in the present work.

Within the driving context till here introduced, the EU-funded Cultural-E project¹ has aimed to develop modular and replicable solutions for plus energy buildings (PEBs), taking into account climatic and cultural diversity, and advancing user-centred design and smart technologies to support the widespread adoption of PEBs across Europe. Based on the definition provided in [13], the plus energy building is “a building capable of producing more renewable energy than it consumes on an annual basis”. Luthander et al. investigate in [14] this perspective through their graphical *Energy Matching Chart*, providing a

complementary and clear assessment of the role that the actual matching between on-site PV generation and building loads plays in meeting nZEB requirements, and by extension, in interpreting PEB definitions. The outlined PEB targets are not only built by upgrading and upsizing the building’s technical systems, but also by pursuing the call for climate- and culture-responsive design, the research for smarter operational strategies that combine advanced control, and consider the integration of occupants’ practices into the building’s energy loop. One of the energy strategies explored within the Cultural-E project involves analysing flexibility in both thermal and electrical domains across different geographical and cultural clusters [15]. In the defined grouping, the climatic factor adopts a reduced classification of the Köppen-Geiger system [16] adapted to building-design applications [17]. Building variability is reduced through a clustering process based on data from the European Building Stock Observatory and other relevant European building stock databases, following the approach described in [18] on the basis of [19].

1.2. State of the art

After outlining the context in which this work is framed, an overview of the topic of building energy-system control is provided, with particular focus on the body of references that support this study and guide the methodological choices. To this end, Table 1 organizes the selected sources according to the major thematic areas that frame and motivate the research presented herein. The focus is on the building, a system equipped with PV renewable generation, storage capacity, deferrable loads, and advanced energy management systems that enable its operational flexibility. The next step of the analysis is to examine the actual operation of this heterogeneous, multi-domain system, where layered controllers govern devices at varying levels of abstraction to ensure service quality and user comfort. The orchestration of the high-level set-points and control logics across several assets such as heat pumps (we think of temperature set-points) and electrical storage (with target net zero energy import from the grid or rated battery exchanged power) is key to unlocking flexibility. While traditional rule-based controls (RBC) have long offered robust and predictable building operation, their

¹ <https://www.cultural-e.eu/>, Accessed Mar. 1, 2024.

Table 1

Multi-dimensional taxonomy of advanced building control approaches, summarizing the principal domains, modeling paradigms, control structures, objective functions and evaluation metrics emerging from the adopted literature, as delineated by the methodological scope and classification choices adopted in this work.

Characteristics	Variants	Literature examples
Control context	Commercial building	[20,21]
	Residential building	[8,22–25]
Energy domain	Thermal	[8,23]
	Electrical	[21,24,25]
Controlled assets	Multi-domain, multi-carrier	[8,22,26,27]
	HP-HVAC systems, thermostatically controlled loads, DHW	[8,20,22,23,26]
	PV-BESS systems	[8,20–22,24–26]
Control paradigms	EV charging, smart appliances	[8,20]
	Classical: RBC, PID/on-off, fuzzy logics	[21,25]
	MPC (subcategories depend on the applied techniques)	[20–24,26]
Model paradigms	White-box (physics-based)	[8,23,26]
	Grey-box (hybrid physics-informed/parameter identification)	[20,24]
	Black-box (fully data-driven using ML techniques)	[20,23]
Optim. objectives	Economic (cost minimization under external price signals)	[20–26]
	Flexibility-driven (DR participation, shedding/shifting/modulation)	[8,20,23]
	Emission-driven (CO ₂ minimization)	[21,24,26]
	Comfort-driven (temperature bounds, discomfort minimization)	[23]
Optim. solvers	Mathematical optimization solvers (LP, NLP, QP...)	[20,21,26]
	Heuristic solvers (GA, PSO)	[22–24]
Perform. metrics	Energy savings, Cost reduction, Peak reduction	[8,20–26]
	Comfort deviations/discomfort hours	[8,23]
	Flexibility indicators (F-Factor, F-Index, F-Function)	[20,23]
	benchmarking vs RBC and baseline control	[21]
Applications	Simulation domain (synthetic building/model of real building)	([24,26]/ [8,20–23,25])
	Laboratory testbeds	[26,28]
	Implementation to real-world pilot	[20,23,25]

static, non-adaptive nature has driven the shift toward model predictive control (MPC), which exploits mathematical models, forecasts, and constrained optimization to anticipate system behavior and deliver more efficient, flexible, and comfort-aware operation [29,30]. Numerous review studies extensively explore these topics, with some adopting a broad and control-agnostic perspective [6,9] and others concentrating specifically on MPC-based approaches [29,31]. Michailidis et al. highlights in [30] that a clear trend is the growing alignment between model complexity and solver sophistication: while early MPC implementations relied on white-box models and QP solvers for transparency and ease of use, the shift toward multi energy domain controls and integrated RES has driven increasing adoption of more flexible grey- and black-box models, often combined with heuristic optimizers [22,24]. According to the overview outlined in Table 1, optimization objectives in building energy control systems consistently gravitate around economic performance, often driven by dynamic electricity prices, market signals, or other cost-minimization criteria [32]. This economic layer is rarely isolated: it typically coexists with additional side objectives such as flexibility provision, thermal-comfort preservation, and emission reduction. These multi-objective requirements may enter the formulation explicitly, through composite objective functions, or implicitly, through operational constraints; however, their coexistence becomes especially

evident during the evaluation phase, where studies systematically assess cost, comfort, flexibility, and environmental impact as parallel dimensions of controller performance. Techno-economic key performance indicators are widely adopted to evaluate through consolidated metrics the energetic performance of the buildings [33]. Self-production and consumption rank among the most common metrics for the effective exploitation of the locally produced renewable energy. Following similar practices, several Flexibility Function (FF) or Indicators have been proposed in literature [6,8]. These indicators generally quantify the relative performance variation achieved when shifting from conventional control strategies to flexibility-enabling ones, typically with respect to a specific objective. The landscape of flexibility metrics has been [29] and remains [30] markedly heterogeneous. As any advanced control framework is known to introduce complexity into the building, detailed analysis is required to estimate potential cost impacts. Some studies specifically addressed this concern by performing proper economic evaluations, which therefore estimate and include CAPEX, OPEX and detailed energy billing schemes as in [20,21]. Such concerns need further integration with the conditions inherited from the PEB paradigm and the related potentials but also the need to match a cost-balanced trade-off as analysed in [34] and differently in [35] for PEB equipped with HP, PV and BESS assets. A final challenge emerging from literature [30,32] concerns the translation of these control formulations into long-term real-building operation: while many studies start from models of existing buildings, only a limited subset succeeds in deploying [23] and especially sustaining for long periods [20] advanced control strategies in real settings. A complementary pathway adopted in [26,28], involves validating advanced control strategies within hybrid laboratory testbenches that combine real physical assets with high-fidelity real-time simulations. In such hardware-in-the-loop environments, the controller interacts simultaneously with actual and simulated assets and network dynamics, enabling reproducible evaluation under conditions that approximate real operation while avoiding the practical constraints of full on-site deployment.

1.3. Main contribution

This work builds upon the methodology introduced in [36], further expanding its scope and applicability. In the current paper, we apply the proposed predictive advanced control to enhance flexibility in a PEB archetype [37] located in four different European geo-clusters and embedding two different thermal controls with increasing complexity and advanced control techniques deployed for the electrical domain. Aided by a simulation environment, we address how the algorithm's performance varies across different climatic, cultural, and system sizing conditions, exploring diversified scenarios and thus offering a generalizable evaluation of its expected effectiveness within the European context. Moreover, we describe the laboratory-scale implementation of our predictive advanced control (PAC) using commercially available devices, designed to emulate a real building at small scale. The year-long dataset collected can be considered as bridging the gap between large-scale real-world implementations [32] and controlled laboratory test benches [26,28]. To summarize, the main contributions are: (i) we extend the demonstration of the effectiveness of a battery storage system control strategy proposed in [36] compared to the rule-based one over a more heterogeneous case study, (ii) present the expected results on a combination of different embedded thermal-domain operations and geographical and cultural clusters aided by year-long simulations, (iii) present the observations of more than one year of operation of a laboratory-scale experimental setup to demonstrate the application of the proposed control on a real system. The rest of the paper presents in Section 2 the modelled energy system, the battery energy storage system control strategies, and thermal domain logics embedded in the adopted consumption electrical profiles. Section 3 reports simulation-based results, and finally Section 4 describes the experimental setup. Finally, conclusions are presented.

Fig. 1. Diagram of the component of the energy system model from [36, Figure 1].

2. Methodology

2.1. Energy system model

We set up a simulation environment to represent a simplified residential building. The defined model was originally introduced in [36, Section II.A] and is here recalled in the simplified schematic of Fig. 1. We concentrate on the electrical domain of the main assets present in the building. Thus, the model replicates the behavior and computes the control strategies of the most critical electrical components. The following devices are considered according to the services they provide: energy consumption (electrical loads), local renewable generation (photovoltaic systems), and electrochemical storage.

The model takes as input the technical specifications of the electrical assets (presence, sizing, nominal values and operational parameters) according to the simulated use case. The photovoltaic system and building load components are generated by providing the model with their respective time-series of power production and consumption. These time-series incorporate geo-cluster-specific information, including climate conditions, consumption behaviors, building typology, and occupant usage patterns. As we limited our modeling to the electrical system, the model and control expressed in the other domains (primarily the thermal domain, for which refer to Section 2.2) are transposed and embedded in the resulting electrical power profile we take here as input. The resulting load consumption includes the heating/cooling, lighting, ventilation, and appliances. Such an approach allows us to focus on the tuning and performance evaluation of only the electrical part, thus simplifying the overall modeling complexity.

At the core of the system represented in Fig. 1 is a hybrid DC-AC inverter, which manages the bidirectional energy flow between the PV array installed on the rooftop and façades of the building, the battery modules, and the building loads. While the PV and load components rely on externally supplied temporal profiles, the battery is internally modelled as part of the energy system. A simplified model based on linear efficiency is used to represent the power converter stages that bridge the AC and DC domains. These converters couple the DC-bus, dedicated to PV generation and storage, with the AC-bus, which supplies the main loads of the building and interfaces with the grid.

We presented in [36] the empirical model we adopted to produce the battery behavior. The model is composed of a reduced-order polynomial and other mathematical expressions as proposed by [38] as extension of the so called Shepherd model [39]. Equations (1) and (2) provide the adopted characteristics respectively modeling the charge ($i^* < 0$) and discharge ($i^* > 0$) phases.

$$V_k = E_0 - K \frac{Q}{Q - it} - K \frac{Q}{it + 0.1 \cdot Q} i^* - R_0 \cdot i_k + A e^{-B \cdot it} \quad (1)$$

$$V_k = E_0 - K \frac{Q}{Q - it} [it + i^*] - R_0 \cdot i_k + A e^{-B \cdot it} \quad (2)$$

The characteristics (battery voltage at time k) are modelled on the basis of the only state of charge (SoC), embedded in the equations by the terms it (actual extracted capacity $it = \sum_{n=0}^k i_n \cdot \Delta t$ in Ah) and Q (max battery capacity), and the applied current i_k associated with a filtered component of such time series i^* with lower dynamics. The update of the battery SoC in the model is performed by the classical Ampere-Hour integral method (Coulomb-counting approach) [40]. That is, the remaining battery charge is normalized by the total nominal capacity according to the following expression:

$$\text{SoC}_{k+1} = \text{SoC}_k - \frac{\Delta t_k \cdot i_k}{Q} \quad (3)$$

The coefficients of the semi-empirical battery model of Eqs. (1) and (2) are estimated from the total charge/discharge characteristics (current/voltage curve) performed at several C-rates using non-linear least square techniques according to the observations introduced in [41] and the application of optimization techniques similar to the approach proposed in [27].

The manufacturer-provided operating parameters complete the set of required inputs to properly execute the energetic model. Concerning the battery simplified model, manufacturer voltage and capacity values² are used to determine the complete charge and discharge conditions of the modelled battery. Further constraints considered for the battery model are maximum operating current, SoC operating range (via the depth of discharge specification), and finally, minimum discharge and maximum charging voltage (compared with the values resulting from the evaluation of the non-linear model).

We refer to the extensive discussion provided by the original authors of the model [38,41] for the complete set of model assumptions and limitations.

The final functional block proposed in Fig. 1 is a building energy management system (BEMS). This component is responsible for the monitoring the system states and the power flows within the building. Such information is combined with external signals to allow a coordination of the available resources.

2.2. Embedded thermal domain control tuning

In this section we discuss the thermal domain modeling and operation that are incorporated into the energy system model of Section 2.1 as pure electrical profiles.

The control strategy of the thermal energy system is designed to meet the building's demands for domestic hot water, space heating, and space cooling, while simultaneously ensuring compliance with indoor comfort requirements. For this purpose, a rule-based control and an advanced control were developed.

The rule-based control (referred to as *BasCtrl*) algorithm is employed to regulate the system, maintaining the indoor air temperature within a narrow comfort band centred around a predefined setpoint. The domestic hot water (DHW) thermal energy storage is charged by the heat pump when the temperature measured by a sensor positioned at 60% of the storage height falls below the setpoint temperature. Charging continues until the sensor temperature reaches a threshold equal to the setpoint plus 5 °C. This rule-based control approach aims to minimize the thermal energy input required to fulfill the building's thermal demands.

The advanced control strategy (*AdvCtrl*) extends the rule-based approach by dynamically adjusting the temperature setpoints for both the DHW storage and the indoor environment. These adjustments are designed to shift thermal loads toward the midday period, when photovoltaic (PV) generation is typically at its peak, thereby aligning energy demand with on-site renewable energy availability. The primary objective of this advanced control is to enhance the interaction between the

² <https://www.vpsolar.com/download/catalog/Storage/Pylontech/US2000C-Pylontech-datasheet-EN.pdf>, Accessed Mar. 1, 2024.

generation systems (i.e., heat pump and PV array), thermal storage, and building envelope to reduce reliance on grid electricity and increase PV self-consumption. To support this goal, it is crucial to anticipate whether the PV system's electricity generation for the following day will exceed or fall short of the building's electrical demand over the same time frame. For this purpose, a simplified predictive model was developed, capable of estimating both the building's electrical consumption and the PV system's electricity production based on weather forecasts.

The projected electrical load \hat{W} for the current day is estimated as a quadratic function of the daily heating degree days (HDD) during the heating season (Eq. 4) and the daily cooling degree days (CDD) during the cooling season (Eq. 5). HDD and CDD values are determined by comparing the average daily ambient temperature with predefined threshold temperatures: 20 °C for the heating season and 15 °C for the cooling season.

$$\hat{W}_{el,winter} = A_{0,H} + A_{1,H} \cdot HDD + A_{2,H} \cdot HDD^2 \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{W}_{el,summer} = A_{0,c} + A_{1,c} \cdot CDD + A_{2,c} \cdot CDD^2 \quad (5)$$

A similar methodology was used to forecast the value of the total daily electrical energy production of the photovoltaic system. The coefficients of the three simplified estimations were individually calibrated for each simulation scenario, using the results obtained from the rule-based control simulations as a reference.

In the proposed advanced control strategy, the setpoint temperature of the domestic hot water storage is increased by 5 K when the forecasted daily photovoltaic electricity production exceeds the forecasted daily electricity demand of the building, and the outdoor temperature is at least 2 K above the predicted daily average temperature. Similarly, the space heating setpoint is elevated by 2 K if the projected daily PV electricity generation reaches at least 50% of the anticipated daily building electricity consumption and the outdoor temperature surpasses the forecasted daily average by 2 K. A nighttime setback strategy is applied wherein the space heating setpoint is reduced by 2 K between 22:00 and 06:00. Additionally, the space cooling setpoint is lowered by 2 K when three conditions are simultaneously met: the daily forecasted PV electricity production exceeds the building's daily electricity consumption, the outdoor temperature is 2 K higher than the forecasted daily average, and the battery storage system is fully charged.

The resulting thermal domain operations are then converted into the electrical profiles of load associated with the heat pump and heating and cooling system of the building. Due to this operation on the outcome of the work done in the thermal domain, we refer to this part of the control tuning as embedded control tuning. More details on the methodology, implementation, and proper tuning of such thermal control are available in [15]. The resulting electrical profiles are then taken as input to the electrical energy model introduced in Section 2.1.

2.3. Predictive advanced control

In Section 2.1 we introduce the building energy management system related to the implemented energy system model in the electrical domain. This component is responsible for the operation of the electrical storage, by generating the charge/discharge rate of the battery.

The battery tracks these setpoints according to its capability and its states are modelled through the empirical model proposed in Section 2.1, properly configured with estimated parameters and manufacturer operative settings. The simulation requires the iterative evaluation of the system components at each point of the input time series. A typical simulation horizon covers one year with time resolution from 15 minutes to 1 hour, with the possibility to run shorter-duration simulations while increasing temporal resolution. The outcome is a dataset adopted to evaluate the performance of the devices that compose the energy system. We compute common key performance indicators (KPIs) across economic, environmental, and overall technical domains [33], including self-consumption, self-production, energy exchanged with the

grid, overall energy use, and CO₂ reduction. Self-consumption and self-production measure local energy utilisation, while energy exchange with grid highlights energy net flows with the external grid. The CO₂ indicator quantifies the reduction (higher values are preferable) in emissions achieved by integrating PV-BESS technologies into the building and applying the proposed control strategy, compared to a baseline scenario that lacks these assets. This indicator does not consider the embodied component.

The standard battery control requires the monitoring of the balance at the building level, storing the excess of locally produced energy and releasing such energy when the direct PV production is not able to cover the entire load of the building. Such baseline operation mode is called rule-based control (RBC) [42] and is kept as reference. We introduced in [36, Section II.B] the so called Predictive Advanced Control (PAC) inspired by the definitions provided in [29]) and with the aim of optimizing the use of the PV-BESS resource according to an external signal. Fig. 2 summarizes the main stages of the proposed PAC. We proceed to briefly outline these phases, while a detailed definition is provided in [36, Section II.B]. The external signal is mapped to a price signal and is selected as indicator of the availability of electricity [43,44] and is assumed to incorporate and implicitly convey information about the state of the grid. The PAC aims at minimizing the energy imported from the grid during high-priced electricity hours by altering the operation of the local battery storage, similar to what was analysed in [45] for a non-residential consumer context. As a result, battery discharge is inhibited in those hours of the day to shift the buffered energy to hours with more profitability according to the defined cost function Eq. (6).

The control is updated iteratively with an interval called control horizon H_c which is fixed as a fraction (i.e., 0.20–0.25) of the prediction horizon H_p [29]. The PAC update computation takes as input the current state of the system ($P_{load}, P_{PV}, SOC_{k=n_0}$ at time $k = n_0$). A first stage requires the construction of the forecast of the system states for the next $k = n_0 + 1, \dots, n_0 + H_p$ future which is defined by the prediction horizon $H_p = 24$ (day-ahead with hourly time resolution). With these inputs, it is possible to use the energy system model to explore the expected evolution of the system in the near future. This evaluation is carried out iteratively, computing the resulting performance of several variations of high-level controls, thus exploring multiple different control scenarios by means of the available model. A heuristic genetic algorithm (GA) optimization technique is adopted to tackle the tuning of the high-level operation of the controlled assets. Fig. 2 reports in the red box the stages of the genetic algorithm as applied in the predictive advanced control resolution. An initialization phase produces a population of possible high-level controls within the admissible parameter ranges. This is followed by the evaluation of the energy system model according to each high-control guess that composes the sampled population at the current generation. The resulting performance concerning the PAC objective is summarized by the introduced cost function Eq. (6).

$$\min f = \sum_{k=n_0+1}^{n_0+H_p} \hat{E}_k \cdot C_k \quad (6)$$

The cost function f results from the product of the predicted energy imported from the grid at the k -iteration time (\hat{E}_k) and the external cost signal (C_k) and is evaluated over the entire prediction horizon. The energy systems model embeds in its definition the operational constraints of each device that were presented in Section 2.1 and are here not expressly defined in the formulation of the minimization problem. This intrinsically adheres to the selected heuristic optimization technique here discussed. Given the selection criteria, the heuristic algorithm reduces the original population by pursuing the survival of individuals (high-level control candidates) with better fitness. The resulting population subset is expanded in the next generation by means of crossover and mutation till obtaining a new population that is fed back to the evaluation stage. This process is repeated iteratively across generations

Fig. 2. Diagram of the proposed predictive advanced control algorithm with the update of the control in the next prediction horizon H_p by using the heuristic optimization technique.

Table 2

Factors combined to generate the $C = 16$ simulated scenarios. Each geo-cluster is associated with a country and city. In this regard, approximations are adopted given project requirements and data availability.

Geo-cluster (Country–City)	Building archetypes	Embedded thermal control (Acronym)	Proposed control
Mediterranean (IT–Bologna)	Low-Rise	Basic Ctrl (<i>BasCtrl</i>)	RBC (Ref)
Sub-arctic (NO–Oslo)	–	Advanced Ctrl (<i>AdvCtrl</i>)	PAC (perfect forecast)
Oceanic (FR/BE–Brussels)	–	–	–
Continental (DE–Stuttgart)	–	–	–

until either the improvement between iterations falls below a defined threshold or a maximum number of generations is reached.

The evaluation of the PAC objective is performed with the indicator F_{KPI} called flexibility key performance indicator [36].

$$F_{KPI} = \frac{\sum_k E_{PAC,HPT}}{\sum_k E_{RBC,HPT}} - 1 \quad (7)$$

The definition in (7) quantifies the normalized reduction of energy imported from the grid during the so-called high-priced time (HPT) thanks to the introduction of the PAC over the baseline RBC. We adopt a threshold value of the 85th percentile of the external signal time-series to clearly determine such high-price hours.

3. Simulation results

3.1. Simulation settings and assumptions

In the framework of the project Cultural-E, the European region is clustered into four climate and cultural geo-clusters. Two reference buildings are examples of the European building stock according to the actual configuration of the demos planned in the project [15].

Table 2 collects the factors considered in the generation of the scenarios explored in the simulation domain. We base the current work on the outcomes of the Cultural-E project, and reduce the case-study collection to a single building archetype (a low-rise multi-family house composed of seven flats). We also retain two different control tuning paradigms for the thermal domain loads, originally formulated and widely discussed

Table 3

Parameters adopted in the simulations and characteristics of the selected building archetype (Table 2) grouped by geo-cluster.

	Units	IT	NO	FR	DE
Number of dwelling	qt.	7	7	7	7
Nominal installed PV	kWp	32.63	31.71	32.63	32.17
BESS capacity	kWh	46.00	16.00	63.00	42.00
Building total yearly consumption	MWh	32.80	46.74	39.94	37.08
PV total yearly production	MWh	38.55	25.99	25.10	29.98
PV-to-Load Ratio	kWp/MWh	0.99	0.68	0.82	0.87
Battery-to-Load Ratio	kWh/MWh	1.40	0.34	1.58	1.13
Storage-to-PV Ratio	kWh/kWp	1.41	0.50	1.93	1.31

in [15], which we take here as input to our simulation as embedded in the adopted electrical profiles. The resulting selection of factors allows us to handle the complexity introduced by the model predictive control while still varying the aspects that we consider critical to have a sufficiently complete view of the behavior of the PAC in the EU region.

The simulation plan requires the execution of a one-year simulation (with hourly time resolution) for each combination of factors which brings the number of total scenarios to $C = 16$. About the proposed control, we always perform one simulation applying the baseline RBC control in the electrical domain. We keep this execution as a baseline for the comparison with the second set of simulations performed applying the proposed PAC control.

Table 3 reports the complete set of parameters that describe the devices in the system adopted for each geo-cluster according to the sizing produced in the framework of the Cultural-E project [15]. Such sizing of the building parameters was obtained through techno-economic evaluation within the prescriptions of the plus energy building (PEB) paradigms and the actual characteristics of the selected building archetype. The size and exposition of PV panels as well as the storage dimension follow precisely this selection process. The load profiles input of the current work results from the dynamic simulation of a building for each geo-cluster based on thermo-physical parameters; thus they incorporate the electrical appliances and the thermal loads supplied by the heat pump according to the detailed building model and the thermal controls described in Section 2.2. Finally, the efficiency adopted for each power converter stage equals $\eta = 0.97$.

Fig. 3. Key Performance Indicators obtained from simulations with rule-based control. Combination of explored embedded thermal controls (Table 2) and geoclusters. For $E_{to\ grid}$ and $E_{from\ grid}$, lower values indicate better performance; for all other indicators, including CO_2 reduction, higher values are preferable.

The Predictive Advanced Control (PAC) introduced in Section 2.3 adopts as external signal the national reference price time series of the country/city that is beyond each geo-cluster according to choices made in the Cultural-E project (Table 2). This signal for the Mediterranean cluster (Italy) is the so called PUN and for the other clusters it is obtained from the European Wholesale Electricity Price Dataset³ referred to the year 2019 with a time resolution of 1h. The PAC prediction horizon H_p is 24 hours and the control horizon H_c respects the 0.2-factor rule discussed in Section 2.3. Perfect forecast assumption is adopted for the prediction of all the time series states required to feed the PAC computation according to the schema in Fig. 2.

3.2. Performance results

We simulate the $C = 16$ scenarios resulting from the combination of factors from Table 2 and present here the results. Here we first summarize the results obtained from the applied embedded thermal domains that serve as inputs to our work. Then we focus on the actual exploitation of energy flexibility by means of the proposed predictive advanced control which is shown to be able to retain the original input KPI.

The results in the Fig. 3 show how a reasoned control in the thermal domain can improve the main observed key performance indicators. This emerges in the figure from the comparison between *BasCtrl* and *AdvCtrl* embedded thermal control. The same data are also reported extensively in Table 4, where the numerical results related to the application of the PAC model are added to provide a complete overview of results from the concatenation of the optimization paradigms described in Sections 2.2 and 2.3 and applied to all $C = 16$ scenarios defined in Table 2. Using those resulting thermal profiles in our electrical energy model we highlight the improvement of all indicators of Fig. 3 moving from the *BasCtrl* to *AdvCtrl* thermal control. This observation on the input results is in line with what is widely discussed and analysed in [15]. There, we highlight how the advanced thermal control is able to introduce a shift of the heat pump work toward the part of the day with higher photovoltaic generation. This shift may lead to an increase in total electricity consumption due to the lower COP of the heat pump, but still it remains justified by the improved utilisation of locally generated electricity.

The analysis proceeds by shifting the focus to the effects of the proposed PAC algorithm and by articulating the discussion into three

consecutive parts. We first address the results obtained from the analysis of the baseline KPIs reported in Table 4. A digression follows, proposing the power profiles and battery control actions of two representative days extracted from one of the simulations to visualize the effects induced by the introduction of the PAC. We finally go back to an indicator driven analysis by commenting on the resulting cost function and tailored flexibility-related indicator.

We consider the KPI values obtained through the thermal control tuning as the baseline and demonstrate according to the results produced in Table 4 and the assumption reported in Section 3.1 that it is possible to retain such building performances even when applying the PAC control on top of the already optimized thermal control. The combination of thermal and the proposed electrical-only optimization does not yield consistent results across all geo-clusters with cases of slightly better performance of the PAC applied to the basic (*BasCtrl*) embedded thermal logic compared to the advanced (*AdvCtrl*) technique and vice versa. We should finally note that in some scenarios, due to both controls having similar working principles, Fig. 4 shows that we can expect a lower performance improvement in terms of the cost function (expressed there as $\Delta f \% = 100 \cdot (f_{PAC} - f_{RBC}) / f_{RBC}$) and F_{KPI} (Eq. (7)) by introducing the PAC operation on top of an already refined thermal control logic.

The results proposed in Table 4 show that the relative variation $abs(\Delta\%)$ of the KPIs due to the introduction of the PAC is, in most cases, lower than 0.8% except for two values originally small in magnitude that manifest higher relative change. Those results are aligned with the outcomes proposed in the work [36], where we further work also outside the assumption of perfect prediction in the PAC evaluation. The range of results obtained for the scenario analysed in [36] by moving from the perfect PV forecast (considered as best case) to the one with the worst performance obtained through persistence was shown there. There we consider the forecast of the only PV production, but a further impact is expected with the introduction of the prediction of the additional components that enter the system such as the building load profile and even the external price signal that enters the cost function computation (6). In the current work we observe from Table 4 across all explored scenarios that, under the assumption of perfect forecast, it is possible to apply the PAC logic with minimal or no impact on the KPIs not targeted by this optimization technique, thereby ensuring the preservation of the performance levels achieved by the PEB building in this regard.

Fig. 5 describes two representative days,⁴ showing the expected effects of the application of the PAC logic against the baseline RBC control. The profiles in the first subplot refer to the production and consumption power behaviors of the building under study. Following this are the charts related to the battery operation pattern in the second row. There, we compare the battery power profile under RBC and the PAC changes. We highlighted the area representing the energy that is shifted due to the operation imposed by the predictive advanced logic. More specifically, we present in violet the area of energy retained in the storage, and in green the area in which this retained energy is moved to and finally used. The time ranges in which this operation takes place are defined in the control output from the PAC and updated iteratively according to the process reproduced in Fig. 2. Last row of Fig. 5 finally provides the external signal that is taken as input for the heuristic optimizer presented in (6). In the proposed representative days, it is possible to appreciate how the application of the PAC effectively shifts battery stored energy from hours with a lower external signal to hours with a higher value of this forcing variable. This holds within the constraints imposed by the boundary conditions in which the controls operate, which are

³ <https://ember-energy.org/data/european-wholesale-electricity-price-data/>, Accessed Jan. 15, 2025.

⁴ The data presented in Fig. 5 derive from the simulations. Specifically, we reproduced two days selected from the IT geo-cluster simulation using the underlying *BasCtrl* thermal control. The external signal threshold reported in the last subplot of Fig. 5 is computed according to the criteria proposed at the end of Section 2.3 to be adopted in (7) and holds only for the specific simulation instance.

Table 4

Key Performance Indicators obtained from simulations of the $C = 16$ scenarios from combination of factors in Table 2. “Thermal Ctrl” refers to the thermal embedded control described in Section 2.2. The column named “RBC/PAC” distinguishes the simulations as follows: the reference rule-based control (RBC) and the proposed predictive advanced control (PAC).

Geo	Thermal Ctrl	RBC/PAC	SC %	SP %	$E_{to\ grid}$ %	$E_{from\ grid}$ %	CO ₂ %
IT	BasCtrl	RBC	67.70	75.90	32.30	24.10	75.90
IT	BasCtrl	PAC	67.70	75.90	32.30	24.10	75.90
IT	AdvCtrl	RBC	71.90	78.40	28.10	21.60	78.40
IT	AdvCtrl	PAC	71.90	78.50	28.10	21.50	78.50
NO	BasCtrl	RBC	57.70	31.30	42.30	68.70	31.30
NO	BasCtrl	PAC	57.70	31.30	42.30	68.70	31.30
NO	AdvCtrl	RBC	63.20	33.90	36.80	66.10	33.90
NO	AdvCtrl	PAC	63.20	33.90	36.80	66.10	33.90
FR	BasCtrl	RBC	88.90	53.80	11.10	46.20	53.80
FR	BasCtrl	PAC	88.40	53.50	11.60	46.50	53.50
FR	AdvCtrl	RBC	91.30	54.60	8.70	45.40	54.60
FR	AdvCtrl	PAC	90.80	54.30	9.20	45.70	54.30
DE	BasCtrl	RBC	69.90	54.10	30.10	45.90	54.10
DE	BasCtrl	PAC	69.80	54.10	30.20	45.90	54.10
DE	AdvCtrl	RBC	73.50	56.00	26.50	44.00	56.00
DE	AdvCtrl	PAC	73.40	56.00	26.60	44.00	56.00

substantially the BESS effective storage capacity (which is finite) and the combination of local PV generation and effective experienced building loads.

Referring to the flexibility indicator defined in (7), which is the indicator directly associated with the performance gains achieved through the PAC application, the overall trend of its relative variation with respect to the rule-based control is summarized in Fig. 4. The figure also reports the improvement in the expected cost function (6), expressed as the relative percentage change when switching from the baseline RBC strategy to the proposed PAC. In both cases, smaller (i.e., more negative) values correspond to enhanced performance. We can identify in Fig. 4 three clusters of results according to the belonging geo-cluster. Overall, a higher improvement (14%) is reported for the Mediterranean case as already shown in [36] for the flexibility-oriented indicator F_{KPI} . Intermediate values are reported for the Continental and Oceanic geo-clusters, which both settle on F_{KPI} in the range of 3 – 4%. The sub-arctic geo-cluster measures no significant results. We present expected potential improvements in terms of indicator limited to the building’s energetic flexibility, such approach explores the technical potential in a best case scenario simulated under the assumption stated so far. While the F_{KPI} indicator highlights relative energy shifts given the definitions presented at the end of Section 2.3, the corresponding improvement in terms of cost function Δf % appears significantly reduced according to the results shown in Fig. 4. Nonetheless, we have to consider that such value represents just the raw output of the optimization procedure over the entire simulation year and cannot be directly mapped to an actual cost saving experienced by the customer as it misses in its implementation any billing scheme definition or more extended financial assessment as presented in [20,21].

The heterogeneous results emerging from Fig. 4 confirm the role not only of the climatic and cultural factors on the performance of predictive advanced controls, but also highlight again the importance of the system design and sizing. Proper sizing is widely accepted as a key factor for achieving better technical performance of a building [22]. The paradigm of the plus energy building boosts the standard sizing criteria that intrinsically enhance and widen the margins for better building performance and potential flexibility while finding trade-off solutions with the economic indicators and constraints [34]. Such constraints and trade-offs emerge in the case scenario of the Sub-Arctic geo-cluster. In the proposed simulations, it is indeed characterized by the combination of a small PV production due to geographical reasons and a combined small battery storage size, due to low exploitability of this technology given the poor local energy production capabilities and intrinsic higher consumption induced again by climatic constraints. A similar reasoning

Fig. 4. Changes observed in the simulation from the introduction of the PAC over the standard RBC control. Respectively, minimized expected cost function f relative percentage change and flexibility key performance indicator Eq. (6) F_{KPI} . Negative values indicate improvement and larger absolute values (i.e., more negative) correspond to better performance.

can be carried out for the results observed for the Oceanic geo-cluster. In this case, it is worth noting that the size of the battery pack alone is not sufficient to determine the success of such PAC algorithms. Thus, expected proper sizing can be considered a necessary but not sufficient condition. The building sized for the Oceanic region, in fact, has a relatively larger battery pack than all the other buildings (Table 5), but is not able to offer better performance in terms of flexibility, probably due to the lower photovoltaic performance linked again to the reference climate profile adopted for this region.

4. Laboratory-scale implementation

The results measured on the Mediterranean cluster suggested continuing this work and this logic by porting it to a real setup built in the laboratory and subjected to external irradiation conditions corresponding to the geographical position of our institute, that is, Bolzano. The objective of this experiment is to demonstrate that it is possible to apply the proposed PAC to a real system composed of commercially available components, appropriately combined to represent a small building and controlled from an external energy management system in such a way

Fig. 5. Two representative days showing the effects of the application of by the PAC control strategy. Positive values indicate power generation, while negative values represent consumption (charging for the BESS). Starting from the top, the four subplots respectively represent the PV production and building load profiles; the battery power profile; the resulting power exchange at the grid interconnection point; and the external signal together with the reference threshold adopted in the computation of (7) for the specific simulation instance.

as to comply with the high-level controls resulting from the estimation done in the PAC algorithm.

4.1. Experimental setup

The laboratory setup includes photovoltaic generation, building load and electrical storage to mirror the complete system installed in a potential building unit. The system is composed of integrating preexisting PV installations with heterogeneous photovoltaic technologies and exposure (Fig. 7) and installing a retrofit AC-coupled storage system. The adopted devices (inverters, batteries) are commercially available products designed for residential and industrial installations. Lacking a real building and related appliances and occupants, the load section is reproduced in hardware using a programmable electronic load that applies a load profile time series to the AC bus. Fig. 6 provides a diagram of the system obtained, while an image of the final installation is presented in Fig. 7. The characteristic sizes of the installed components are reported in Table 5 according to the manufacturer's documentation.⁵ The resulting system represents a scaled version of a building, within the limitations imposed by the laboratory infrastructure for this project and by the modularity of the available commercial systems adopted (the resulting configuration still retains approximately similar ratios, as reported in Tables 3 and 6), aiming at replicating, as closely as possible, the building proposed for the Mediterranean geo-cluster context described in the first column of Table 3.

A standard industrial computer⁶ acts as a building energy management system (BEMS) Fig. 6 and is responsible for the integration of the devices and the relative coordination within the laboratory infrastructure. We integrate the communication with the retrofit inverter via a semi-custom Modbus implementation over RS485. The same device also provides all the states collected from the battery modules over the CAN bus. The communication with the electronic load occurs via standard SCPI over TCP/IP. As for the pure simulation part, Python is selected as the programming language in the laboratory setup. Data are exchanged both over HTTPs requests toward a remote InfluxDB database that acts as long-term storage and via MQTTs protocol to a local broker used for live operation and to exchange controls among the different pieces of

Table 5

Technical specifications of the components of the system represented in Fig. 6. Inverter data from manufacturer's datasheet. Battery information from inverter manufacturer's documentation.

	Value	Units
PV max power	4.4	kW
Retrofit inverter max power	3	kW
Retrofit inverter η_{max}	0.94	
Retrofit inverter max DC current	65	A
BESS capacity	3x2.4	kWh
BESS capacity	3x50	Ah
BESS DOD	80	%
BESS module max current	25	A
BESS module reference voltage	48	V
Electronic load max power	1.8	kVA

software that manage via low level communication the two controlled devices. The installed computer is also responsible for the computation of the PAC control and the update of the relative control directive at each control-horizon expiration.

We apply the same timeline for the computation of the PAC update as is done in the simulation regime and described in Section 3.1 with 4 updates of the control rule per day and a prediction horizon of 24 hours.

4.2. Laboratory result observations

We let the PAC operate the system autonomously between July 2023 and December 2024 by cyclically applying the same load profiles and external signals available with a limited length of a year. The experimental results presented here refer to a sub-time window with an exact duration of one calendar year between January 2024 and December of the same year. Those indicators calculated and reported in Table 6 refer to a real year (2024) and the synthetic signals applied to the hardware are repeated only once.

The embedded thermal control is not explicitly simulated in the outdoor implementation, and we simply assume the adopted electrical profile incorporates the baseline thermal part. We applied the consumption profile resulting from the Mediterranean simulation with basic embedded thermal control (*BasCtrl*) scaled down by a factor of seven to match the size of the available system. Power values exceeding the maximum capacity of the electronic load were approximated to that

⁵ <https://www.zcsazzurro.com/it/documentazione/azzurro-retrofit-storage-inverter-3000sp>, Accessed Feb. 7, 2022.

⁶ Specification: CPU Intel i5-6500TE, 4GB memory, OS Debian 11, Python version 3.9.2.

Fig. 6. Schematic of the components of the system object of the implementation of the PAC and layers and protocols that allows the interconnection between devices.

Fig. 7. Image of devices included in the setup within the laboratory facilities. On the left, the retrofit inverter is wall-mounted and in the rack from the top the electronic load, the industrial computer and at the bottom the three battery modules connected in parallel. On the two images on the right: the pre-existing PV field.

maximum power. The external signal adopted in the PAC is the price signal used in the simulations for the Italian geo-cluster.

The laboratory implementation proved to be stable over time and it was possible to collect data over the entire operating period. The data collected and reported here come directly from the devices integrated into the laboratory control system, as well as by acquiring data directly from the retrofit inverter and the electronic load.

Based on the collected dataset, it was possible to calculate the main KPIs reported in Table 6 similarly to what was proposed in Table 4 for the simulation tests. Notice that it is not possible to operate a direct comparison between the simulated scenarios and the laboratory setup as the experimental setup is not an exact replica of the simulation scenario although it is comparable in many of the parameters described before. Moreover, we are operating in real climatic conditions connected to the actual laboratory location. We observe a round-trip losses of the battery around 13% and of the entire system composed of retrofit inverter and batteries around 23% which are in line with what is reported in [46] and [47]. Fig. 8 reports the obtained operation of the inverter and highlights the charge phase during the first part of the day (hours of the day reported on the x-axis, each day is a row on the y axis, actual power values reported by means of colours). The remaining solar energy is not exploited as the battery is fully charged. The stored energy is then released when the PV production is not enough to cover the building loads. This reproduces the standard operation of the inverter with

Table 6

Laboratory result observations. One year of observation KPIs. Ratios similar to the ones proposed in Table 3. There they are computed on the profiles taken as input, here they are evaluated a posteriori on the data resulting from the one-year observation and are therefore presented among the resulting observations.

	Value	Units
Total yearly consumption	4.53	MWh
PV total yearly production	5.78	MWh
Self consumption (SC)	60.26	%
Self production (SP)	66.46	%
$E_{to\ grid}$	39.56	%
$E_{from\ grid}$	33.46	%
PV-to-Load Ratio	0.97	kWp/MWh
Battery-to-Load Ratio	1.59	kWh/MWh
Storage-to-PV Ratio	1.63	kWh/kWp

Fig. 8. One year operation. Power reported from the retrofit inverter from Fig. 6. Positive values during battery discharge, negative values during battery charge.

the rule-based control. Applying the PAC, the algorithm induces a shift of the stored energy to hours with high-priced energy. As this typically holds in early morning and early evening hours according to the Italian energy price profile, we observe a shift of the energy from the night to the morning and from the afternoon to the evening time. The PAC makes the system retain the charge for 10% of the observed time during the 1-year experiment. It is possible to spot those events in the chart in Fig. 9, where we identify the non-standard operation induced by the PAC

Fig. 9. Inverter operation mode during the one-year observation window. Each colour represents a device status (follows the most relevant): 0: ‘Wait - Standby State’, 2: ‘Charge State’, 4: ‘Discharge State’. We inserted status code -1 to highlight the actual operation of the PAC that actively alters the baseline behavior of the device to retain battery charge for more profitable hours. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

with the status code -1 and consequently the darker red colour in the colourmap indicator. We can perform an analysis of each online simulation generated during the iterative computation of optimal control. This analysis provides insights into the expected performance improvements in real-time estimation, which then supports the potential adoption of the PAC directive over the standard rule-based control. Over the period of observation, we count about 1500 control updates, with 86% indicating an expected improvement in the cost function by applying the PAC, as predicted by the values used in the control update calculations. When excluding marginal improvements, about half of the simulations show a significant expected reduction in the value of the cost function, with relative improvements ranging from 0.5% to 40%. It is important to note that large relative improvements often occur on small absolute values of the cost function. Based on simulations, a realistic improvement in the cost function for the specific case can reach up to 3% over the annual horizon (best-case scenario) as reported in Fig. 4. Additionally, an improvement in the F_{KPI} is expected to be of the order of 14% under best-case scenario regarding modeling and forecast accuracy.

5. Conclusions

Building blocks are increasing their role in the evolution of the energy system, by not only reducing energy demands through energy efficiency solutions, but also gaining an active role with their flexibility potential. In this work, we extend the application of the predictive advanced control strategy for Plus Energy Building flexibility introduced in [36], by also including different thermal control strategies and considering four EU geo-cluster. The simulation assessment of an archetype building equipped with a PV-BESS system and a Building Energy Management System (BEMS) highlights notable differences in flexibility improvements across geo-clusters. The Mediterranean cluster shows the highest enhancement, with a 14% increase in the flexibility index. In contrast, the Continental and Oceanic clusters exhibit moderate improvements, both ranging between 3% and 4%, while the Subarctic cluster demonstrates no significant gains. These findings underscore two key insights: firstly, the influence of climatic and cultural factors on the effectiveness of the proposed predictive control strategy; and secondly, the critical importance of appropriate system design and sizing in optimizing performance. The PEB paradigm redefines conventional

sizing criteria, inherently expanding the potential for enhanced building performance and increased flexibility. This approach facilitates the identification of trade-offs with economic constraints encountered in the sizing phase. Such limitations and compromises become particularly evident in the Sub-Arctic geo-cluster scenario.

The promising outcomes observed in the cluster focused on the Mediterranean region encouraged us to pursue this line of investigation further by implementing the simulated approach in a laboratory-scale system built using commercially available products. The system’s operation was monitored over one year using real data, recording the ability to shift battery-stored energy toward high-priced hours, with non-standard induced inverter operations observed 10% of the time, highlighting the system’s responsiveness under real-world conditions.

This work provided the opportunity to refine theoretical assumptions through practical experimentation on a real system, reinforcing the simulation outcomes and stressing current limitations. It also highlighted the trade-offs between the complexity of implementing such advanced systems and the potential performance gains, all while maintaining compliance with standard energy performance indicators. A dedicated financial assessment could further quantify the simulation-driven estimates of real end-user cost savings and evaluate the feasibility of translating these results into real-world applications. Further efforts are also required to optimize the models used to simulate the real system, with particular attention to improving their alignment with actual behavior, focusing especially on the electrical storage technology.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Enrico Dalla Maria: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Francesco Turrin:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Annamaria Belleri:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Grazia Barchi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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